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A TOX modulation phenotype associated with mismatch repair.

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CTLA4 and TOX4 were activated upon complete loss (deletion) of MSH2 in human cells. The data supported development of a general principle which states that loss of genomic stability and transformation that results from that instability is recognized as non-self and summarily marked for destruction by the immune system.